

Impact of antenatal steroid treatment on steroidogenic function and apoptotic remodeling in the suprarenal cortex of neonatal rats

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Abstract

Background: Antenatal corticosteroids are frequently administered during pregnancy for fetal lung maturation and the management of maternal inflammatory or autoimmune diseases and may influence neonatal suprarenal development.

Objective: To evaluate the effects of prenatal dexamethasone and hydrocortisone on suprarenal cortical structure and steroidogenic acute regulatory protein (StAR) expression at postnatal days 1 and 15.

Methods: Sixty pregnant rats were allocated based on gestational timing (early or late), treatment (control, dexamethasone 1 mg/kg, hydrocortisone 10 mg/kg), and postnatal age, forming 12 experimental subgroups. Neonatal suprarenal glands were examined for histological changes using hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining, StAR immunohistochemistry, and terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase dUTP nick end labeling (TUNEL) assay.

Results: Dexamethasone significantly reduced StAR expression compared with the control (0.2193 ± 0.0336 vs. 0.7662 ± 0.0692 , $p < 0.001$), with a more pronounced effect following late gestational exposure. Apoptosis was markedly increased in the treated groups.

Conclusion: Antenatal glucocorticoid treatment induces suprarenal alterations that are both time- and drug-dependent, with marked effects observed in dexamethasone-treated groups.

Keywords

dexamethasone, glucocorticoids, hydrocortisone, neonates, suprarenal gland, TUNEL

Introduction

Corticosteroids administered during pregnancy are widely used in clinical practice and may significantly influence fetal suprarenal development. Prolonged maternal corticosteroid therapy is needed for several conditions during pregnancy, such as idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura (ITP), Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis, systemic lupus erythematosus, Addison's disease, and rheumatological problems (Kurtoğlu et al. 2011; Jaafar et al. 2025). Although it is clinically effective, such treatment exposes the fetus to exogenous glucocorticoids (Chen and Wang 2024). In addition, prenatal corticosteroids are routinely administered in obstetrics to promote fetal lung maturation in cases of preterm delivery (Lim et al. 2025) and are a cornerstone in the management of fetal congenital adrenal hyperplasia (Kendirici et al. 2025). Despite these benefits, concerns remain regarding potential long-term effects on fetal suprarenal development and function (Babović et al. 2024).

Glucocorticoid (GC) release, production, and secretion from the suprarenal cortex are controlled by the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal axis (Thau et al. 2023). Adrenocorticotropic hormone (ACTH) is released from the anterior pituitary gland, which is controlled by corticotropin-releasing hormone (CRH) from the hypothalamus; ACTH stimulates the suprarenal cortex to produce steroids. An increase in cortisol levels in the blood acts as negative feedback on the hypothalamus, reducing the release of CRH. ACTH acts on the extracellular membrane G protein receptors in the suprarenal cortex, leading to suprarenal suppression (Improda et al. 2025), with a reduction in both fetal suprarenal gland volume and steroid synthesis (He et al. 2023).

Exogenous GCs such as hydrocortisone, used at high doses or for long periods, can saturate the placental enzyme 11 β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type 2 (11 β -HSD2), and, as a result, high concentrations of hydrocortisone can cross the placental barrier, causing significant suppression of the fetal adrenal glands (Iatif Al-Hussainy and Khalaf 2016). Hydrocortisone shares the same chemical structure as cortisol, making it the most similar synthetic GC to the natural adrenal hormone (Deng et al. 2019). This close resemblance is why it is considered a physiological form of synthetic GC, leading to reduced endogenous cortisol production and adrenal suppression (Nachawi et al. 2024).

On the other hand, dexamethasone is not inactivated by placental 11 β -HSD2; it can easily cross from the dam to the fetus through the placenta, effectively suppressing ACTH secretion in neonates (Nowotny et al. 2024). Dexamethasone has similar maternal–fetal pharmacokinetic properties. Dexamethasone and betamethasone have higher affinities (7.1- and 5.4-fold, respectively) for the corticosteroid receptor than cortisol (Kemp et al. 2016). Dexamethasone is a highly effective GC, with a half-life of 36–54 h, while hydrocortisone has lower efficacy, with a half-life of less than 12 h (Yasir et al. 2023). Cortisol has a strong affinity for the mineralocorticoid receptor (MR), while dexamethasone's affinity is 3–5 times lower for MR

than that of cortisol. Corticosterone has a 3–5 times lower affinity for the glucocorticoid receptor (GR) compared with the affinity of dexamethasone for GR (Paragliola et al. 2017).

GCs can reduce mitotic activity in the adrenal cortex, particularly in the zona fasciculata (FZ) and zona reticularis (ZR). This suggests that prenatal GC exposure may decrease cell division within the suprarenal cortex, potentially affecting its overall size and structure (Nicolaidis and Chrousos 2023).

Adrenal steroidogenesis depends on the transport of cholesterol by steroidogenic acute regulatory protein (StAR) from the outer mitochondrial membrane to the inner mitochondrial membrane, where the side-chain cleavage enzyme (CYP11A1, P450_{scc}) catalyzes the first and rate-limiting step of steroidogenesis (cholesterol conversion to pregnenolone). Pregnenolone is subsequently transferred to the endoplasmic reticulum (ER), where additional enzymatic reactions lead to the synthesis of steroid hormones (Kater et al. 2022).

Current research has raised the possibility of functional and morphological changes in the neonatal suprarenal cortex after gestational GC treatment (Chen and Wang 2024). The major adverse effect of concern is the activation of the cellular apoptotic pathway, leading to permanent functional and structural impairment of the neonatal suprarenal gland. Apoptosis is a programmed natural cell death involved in the development and regression of tissues. Prenatal GC exposure can alter the balance of apoptotic cells in the adrenal cortex, leading to changes in cell density and tissue architecture (Spencer et al. 1999).

Although the effects of antenatal GCs on fetal adrenal development have been widely discussed, some points remain unclear. These include, in particular, limited information on how early versus late gestational exposure influences fetal adrenal development within the same experimental model, and few studies have directly compared dexamethasone with hydrocortisone.

In addition, postnatal adrenal changes, especially between day 1 and day 15, remain poorly characterized.

Therefore, the present study aims to investigate timing-dependent, age-related, and drug-specific effects of antenatal GC exposure on neonatal suprarenal cortical development, integrating histological changes with steroidogenic activity, StAR expression, and apoptosis.

This study includes the comparative effect of dexamethasone and hydrocortisone administration in both early and late phases of gestation on neonatal suprarenal structure and steroidogenic activity at postnatal day 1 and day 15. To the best of the authors' knowledge, no single experimental model has systematically investigated the effects of early versus late gestational timing, combined GC comparisons (dexamethasone versus hydrocortisone), and postnatal assessment at days 1 and 15.

This study employed rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) as the experimental model due to their short gestation period, well-characterized suprarenal development, and suitability for controlled prenatal interventions. The rat model en-

ables precise timing and dosing of steroid administration, which would be challenging in human studies.

The selection of StAR as an immunohistochemical marker was based on its essential role in adrenal steroidogenesis, where it mediates the rate-limiting step of cholesterol transport into mitochondria. StAR expression is a reliable functional biomarker for assessing suprarenal cortical activity, especially in response to prenatal GC exposure.

Materials and methods

Ethical approval statement

All experimental procedures were conducted in accordance with the guidelines of the National Institutes of Health (NIH) for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals. The research protocol was reviewed and approved by the Research Ethics Committee/Institute Review Board (REC/IRB) of the College of Medicine, Al-Nahrain University, Iraq, under approval No. 20250372.

Experimental animals and care

Sixty female rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) weighing 250 ± 50 g and 12 adult male rats used exclusively for mating were obtained from the institutional animal house of the Biotechnology Research Center, Al-Nahrain University, Baghdad, Iraq. All animals were selected as healthy. All animals used were bred, raised, and maintained in this institutional facility and were not privately owned by any person, farm, or external institution. In light of this, informed consent from private owners was not applicable.

Animals were housed in standard polypropylene cages with stainless-steel lids and wood-shaving bedding, replaced twice weekly. Clinical trial number: not applicable.

Appropriate housing conditions, including dark and light cycles and room temperature control, were maintained by trained personnel to minimize animal suffering and, as much as possible, to reduce animal use.

Environmental enrichment, including nesting materials and cardboard tubes, was provided to reduce stress and allow natural behaviors. The rats were housed in an animal facility, which was maintained at 18–22 °C with a 12 h light/dark cycle. Tap water and standard rodent pellets were available *ad libitum*. Daily health checks were performed by trained personnel. All animals were acclimatized for 1 week prior to experiments (Zohny et al. 2023).

According to the trio mating system with a 2:1 female-to-male ratio (Flagel et al. 2002), females were placed overnight with males for mating in clean plastic cages under controlled conditions. Positive vaginal swab results at 07:00 a.m. indicated successful mating, and that day was considered gestational day zero.

Pregnant rats were housed under identical environmental conditions, including temperature, light/dark cy-

cle, and diet. Cages were placed in similar locations and rotated regularly to avoid positional bias.

Drugs used

The doses and timing of steroid administration were selected based on previous studies showing significant effects on neonatal suprarenal gland development. Early and late treatments allowed comparison of critical developmental windows. Dexamethasone phosphate (Decadron, MEDOCHEM LTD, Cyprus) was administered intraperitoneally at a dose of 1 mg/kg once daily (Stojanoski et al. 2006; Salman et al. 2025). Hydrocortisone sodium succinate (E.I.P.I.C.O, Egypt) was administered intraperitoneally to pregnant female rats at a dose of 10 mg/kg/day, divided into three doses (Erskine et al. 1979; Medicine Evaluation Board 2021). Control groups received intraperitoneal normal saline at 1 mL/kg once daily during the same experimental period.

Although comparable GC doses have been employed in experimental models, their specific effects on the suprarenal cortex have not been systematically investigated, particularly with respect to gestational timing and early postnatal development. This represents a notable gap that the present study aims to address.

The doses of dexamethasone (1 mg/kg/day) and hydrocortisone (10 mg/kg/day) were selected based on previously published rodent studies utilizing similar or comparable GC ranges that demonstrated measurable biological activity. While these studies did not specifically target the suprarenal gland, their findings confirm that the selected doses are within pharmacologically active experimental ranges.

In addition, dose selection was supported by interspecies dose conversion using body surface area normalization (human equivalent dose, HED), in accordance with established pharmacological principles described in *Practical Manual of Experimental and Clinical Pharmacology* (Medhi and Prakash 2010). Based on this approach, the selected doses approximate clinically relevant GC exposure levels.

From a clinical perspective, the interpretation of these doses was guided by the pharmacological characteristics of each agent. Dexamethasone is a potent, long-acting synthetic GC commonly used in antenatal corticosteroid therapy, whereas hydrocortisone is a shorter-acting physiological GC widely used in anti-inflammatory and replacement regimens. Therefore, the selected dosing strategy enables a meaningful comparison between the effects of synthetic and physiological GCs within a controlled experimental framework.

Dexamethasone and control saline were administered between 9:00 and 10:00 a.m. daily. Hydrocortisone was administered in three divided doses throughout the day (every 8 h) according to the experimental protocol.

All procedures were performed with gentle handling to minimize discomfort. Daily health checks were performed, and any animal showing signs of severe deterioration or distress would have undergone humane euthanasia; however, this was not required.

Experimental design

The pregnant rats were randomly allocated to the control and treated groups using simple randomization. Each animal was assigned a number, and random allocation was performed using a random-number table to ensure unbiased distribution. Pregnant rats were divided into two groups depending on the timing of steroid administration during the first week of gestation (GD1–GD7). For postnatal evaluation, separate maternal groups were used for each time point, resulting in six independent experimental groups as follows (Fig. 1A, B). The postnatal day 1 groups were as follows:

- ECont: control group received 1 mL/kg normal saline ($n = 5$),
- EDx: received 1 mg/kg dexamethasone ($n = 5$),

- EHD: received 10 mg/kg hydrocortisone ($n = 5$), postnatal day 15 groups:
- ECont: control group received 1 mL/kg normal saline ($n = 5$),
- EDx: received 1 mg/kg dexamethasone ($n = 5$),
- EHD: received 10 mg/kg hydrocortisone ($n = 5$).

Pregnant rats were divided into two groups depending on the timing of steroid administration during the last week of gestation (GD15–GD21). For postnatal evaluation, separate maternal groups were used for each time point, resulting in six independent experimental groups as follows (Fig. 1A, B). The postnatal day 1 groups were as follows:

- LCont: control group received 1 mL/kg normal saline ($n = 5$),
- LDx: received 1 mg/kg dexamethasone ($n = 5$),

Figure 1. A. Schematic representation of the experimental design illustrating prenatal treatment periods (early and late gestation), drug administration, and postnatal evaluation at days 1 and 15; B. Schematic representation of the experimental design showing the distribution of animals according to gestational timing, treatment groups, and postnatal age, resulting in 12 experimental subgroups.

- LHd: received 10 mg/kg hydrocortisone ($n = 5$), postnatal day 15 groups:
- LCont: control group received 1 mL/kg normal saline ($n = 5$),
- LDx: received 1 mg/kg dexamethasone ($n = 5$),
- LHd: received 10 mg/kg hydrocortisone ($n = 5$).

Steroid treatments were administered to the pregnant dams according to the experimental protocol. Because offspring derived from the same dam are not fully statistically independent, one neonate was randomly selected from each litter to minimize potential litter effects. Consequently, a total of 60 neonatal rats at postnatal days 1 and 15, obtained from multiple pregnant dams, were included in the analyses. The sample sizes were determined in accordance with previous studies. The investigators conducting the experimental procedures, outcome assessments, and data analyses were aware of the group allocation and were not blinded during the study.

The primary outcome measures used to determine the sample size were histopathological changes, StAR marker expression levels, and the number of apoptotic cells in the suprarenal gland.

The first and last weeks of pregnancy were selected because they represent two critical developmental windows of the fetal suprarenal gland. The early week corresponds to the initial formation and differentiation of suprarenal cortical zones, while the last week represents the maturation phase, when the gland becomes functionally more active. Therefore, these periods are the most sensitive to steroid exposure. Postnatal day 1 was chosen to assess the immediate structural and functional effects of prenatal GC exposure at birth, when suprarenal responsiveness is still highly dependent on maternal influence. Postnatal day 15 was selected to evaluate whether these alterations persist, progress, or begin to recover during early neonatal development as the HPA axis matures.

Anesthesia and surgical procedure

The suprarenal glands were collected from 60 neonatal rats on postnatal days 1 and 15 according to the experimental design. The sample size was determined in accordance with previous studies. Animals were euthanized by exposure to 2% isoflurane-soaked cotton placed in an airtight chamber for 5 min, a concentration sufficient to induce deep anesthesia followed by death. Complete loss of reflexes and absence of response to stimuli were confirmed prior to any surgical manipulation. A thoracotomy was then performed, and the heart was excised as a secondary physical method to ensure death, in accordance with the AVMA Guidelines for the Euthanasia of Animals.

Following confirmation of death, the ventral abdominal wall was opened by a midline incision along the linea alba from the xiphoid process to the pubic symphysis. The right and left suprarenal glands were carefully dissected after excising the anterior organs.

No additional analgesia was administered, as euthanasia with high-concentration isoflurane followed by cardiac

excision ensures complete loss of consciousness and death prior to tissue collection, preventing any pain or distress.

Histological preparations

After the suprarenal glands were collected, they were immediately fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin for 24 h and then processed according to standard procedures for paraffin sectioning: dehydration, clearing, impregnation, and embedding. Sections of 5 μm were stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) (Suvarna et al. 2018). Slides were examined and photographed using a light microscope (LEICA DM 750, Germany) with 40 \times and 100 \times objective lenses. Fields were captured using a digital camera (MC500).

Immunohistochemical protocol and examination

The marker used to detect StAR protein expression was the anti-StAR antibody (ab203193, Abcam, UK). Cross sections of the central portion, measuring 5 μm in thickness, were taken from the fetal suprarenal glands. After deparaffinization and antigen retrieval, the sections were treated with a primary antibody, anti-StAR diluted 1:200, for 1 h according to the recommended protocol, followed by biotinylated goat anti-polyvalent and streptavidin peroxidase. Thirty field images of immunohistochemically labeled slides for each group were captured using the same light microscope and camera used for H&E staining. Images were analyzed using Aperio ImageScope v.11 software to assess total positivity in four randomly selected peripheral fields of the suprarenal cortex at 40 \times magnification. Quantitative analysis of StAR immunohistochemistry was performed using the positive pixel count algorithm. A total of 30 readings were obtained for each experimental group. Mean values were then calculated and expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD).

Immunofluorescence protocol and examination (TUNEL assay)

TUNEL staining was performed according to the manufacturer's instructions. The TUNEL assay was selected as a reliable method for detecting DNA fragmentation associated with apoptosis in the suprarenal cortex. The suprarenal gland tissue sections were examined using a TUNEL assay kit (TUNEL Assay Kit-BrdU-Red ab66110, Abcam, UK). Tissue sections, 5 μm thick, were deparaffinized and rehydrated. Then, slides were treated with proteinase K, DNA labeling solution, and antibody solution (anti-BrdU Red antibody + rinse buffer), followed by DNA counterstaining. Fluorescence imaging was performed using a ZEISS AXIO Imager Z2 fluorescence microscope. DAPI was used as a blue nuclear counterstain to identify viable cells, while apoptotic cells labeled by the TUNEL assay (BrdU-Red) were visualized using a Texas Red filter (red channel). Images were captured separately for each channel and merged to generate composite images for analysis.

All fluorescence images were captured under identical imaging conditions to ensure consistency and comparability between experimental groups.

Quantitative analysis was performed by counting TUNEL-positive nuclei (bright red) in the suprarenal cortex in four randomly selected peripheral fields at 40× magnification. A total of 30 fields were analyzed from five neonates per group.

Outcomes measured

Primary outcomes included:

1. Histological structure of the suprarenal cortices by H&E staining.
2. StAR protein expression by immunohistochemistry.
3. Apoptotic cell counts by TUNEL assay.

All live neonates were included in the study, and the only exclusion criterion was the presence of non-viable dead neonates at birth, which was not predetermined but was applied naturally during sample collection. Only dead neonates were excluded from the analysis. The exact number of neonates analyzed in each experimental group was $n = 5$ for each treatment and age point.

Statistical analysis

The Shapiro–Wilk test was used to assess the normality of data distribution prior to statistical analysis. SPSS software version 23 was used for data analysis, and data were expressed as mean \pm SD. Differences between groups were evaluated using one-way ANOVA, followed by Tukey's post hoc test to identify significant differences between multiple groups. An independent *t*-test was used to compare two groups when appropriate. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results

General microscopic features of the suprarenal gland cortex (H & E)

Postnatal day 1

At postnatal day 1, sections of the adrenal glands in the control group displayed normal histological architecture, characterized by a developed fibrous capsule and a well-differentiated cortex composed of three anatomically distinct zones: the zona glomerulosa (ZG) immediately beneath the capsule, the zona fasciculata (ZF) forming the thickest layer, and the zona reticularis (ZR) surrounding the medulla.

In contrast, prenatal treatment with dexamethasone (EDx) during the first week of gestation showed suprarenal cortical necrosis, evidenced by ghost cells, inflammatory cell infiltration, and pyknotic nuclei, reflecting disruption of the normal cortical architecture. Vacuolated cytoplasm, multinucleated giant cells, and dilated blood vessels were

observed across all three cortical zones, more prominently in the EDx group than in the EHD group. Both the EDx and EHD groups showed a reduction in cortical thickness.

More pronounced necrosis and apoptosis were observed in groups treated during the third week of gestation (LDx and LHd), with marked degenerative changes, including cortical thinning and disruption of the normal zonal architecture. The LDx group showed extensive inflammatory cell infiltrates, multinucleated giant cells, pyknosis, karyorrhexis, spindle-shaped nuclei, and cortical resorption. The LHd group exhibited intracellular edema and degenerative changes, but to a lesser extent than the LDx group, as shown in Fig. 2.

Postnatal day 15

By postnatal day 15, the control group showed clear maturation and distinct organization of the adrenal cortical zones. The zona glomerulosa consisted of ovoid cell clusters, the zona fasciculata showed polyhedral cells arranged in straight radial cords, and the zona reticularis appeared as irregularly arranged cells.

In the EDx group, marked alterations were observed, including reduced cortical thickness associated with fibrotic changes, vascular dilation with hemorrhage, and focal areas of necrosis. In contrast, the EHD group showed partial preservation of cortical architecture, although cytoplasmic vacuolation and degenerative changes remained evident.

In both the LDx and LHd groups, the histological changes observed in all three zones were comparable to those seen in the EDx and EHD groups at postnatal day 15. A relative reduction in the thickness of the suprarenal cortex was noted, which was more pronounced in the LDx group, with evident necrosis characterized by fibrous bands, inflammatory cell infiltration, and areas of cortical resorption. The affected cells exhibited spindle-shaped nuclei and karyorrhexis.

The LHd group revealed less severe changes, including vascular congestion, cytoplasmic vacuolation, hemorrhage, and interstitial edema (Fig. 3).

Immunohistochemical evaluation of StAR protein in suprarenal cortex

The results of StAR protein expression in the treatment groups, including a comparison of the intensity of expression with the control groups and among all experimental groups, are summarized in Figs 4, 5 and Table 1.

Immunohistochemical expression of StAR protein showed strong reactivity in the suprarenal cortex, and quantitative analysis indicated that the highest expression was observed in all control groups (ECont and LCont) at both postnatal day 1 (0.7662 ± 0.0692 and 0.7344 ± 0.0701 , respectively) and day 15 (0.7285 ± 0.0653 and 0.7020 ± 0.0465 , respectively). StAR expression in the ECont and LCont groups at day 15 significantly decreased ($p < 0.05$) compared with the ECont and LCont groups at day 1, while no significant difference was found between

Figure 2. Cross sections of the suprarenal cortex at postnatal day 1 (H&E, 40 \times). **A.** The control group shows a developed capsule (C) surrounding a thin zone, ZG, and a thick zone, ZF, with ZR surrounding a central medulla (M); **B.** The EDx group shows inflammatory cell aggregation (circle), pyknosis (arrow), wide sinusoids (square-headed arrow), and vacuolated cells (circle-headed arrow) in ZR and ZF; **C.** The EDx group shows ghost cells (dotted arrow) in ZG and ZF, as well as expansion in the main blood vessels (square-headed arrow) and multinucleated giant cells (arrowhead); **D.** A section of the EHD group shows shrinkage and wide sinusoids (square-headed arrow) in all cortical zones; **E.** The LDx group shows areas of necrosis with resorption (arrow), vacuolated cells (circle-headed arrow), and multinucleated giant cells (arrowhead); **F.** The LDx group shows inflammatory cell aggregation (circle) in all zones (40 \times); **G.** The LDx group shows reduced cortical thickness with spindle-shaped nuclei (rotated arrow), pyknotic cells (arrow), and expanded blood vessels (square-headed arrow) (100 \times); **H.** A section of the LHD group shows connective tissue edema (arrow) and cell degeneration (circle-headed arrow) (40 \times).

Figure 3. Cross section of the suprarenal cortex at postnatal day 15 (H&E, 40×). **A.** The control group shows ZG and ZF cells arranged in straight columns and ZR cells arranged as anastomosing cords with sinusoids between them (square-headed arrow); **B.** The EDx group shows fibrosis and shrinkage in cortical zones (star), congested sinusoids (square-headed arrow), and multinucleated giant cells (arrowhead); **C.** The EHd group shows an improvement in cortical cell architecture, with few cytoplasmic vacuoles (circle-headed arrow); **D.** The EHd group shows ZF and ZR with cell degeneration and cytoplasmic vacuolation (circle-headed arrow) and multinucleated giant cells (arrowhead); **E.** The LDx group shows shrinkage with fibrosis (star), congested sinusoids (square-headed arrow), and resorption areas (arrow) along the cortical zones; **F.** The LDx group shows cytoplasmic vacuolation (circle-headed arrow) in ZR and spindle-shaped nuclei (rotated arrow), with expanded sinusoids (square-headed arrow); **G.** The LDx group shows inflammatory cell aggregation (circle), with hemorrhage (arrowhead) and connective tissue edema (arrow) in ZF; **H.** The LHd group shows hemorrhage (circle), congested sinusoids (square-headed arrow), and vacuolated cytoplasm (circle-headed arrow) in ZF.

Figure 4. Immunohistochemical reaction of StAR protein expression in the suprarenal cortex at postnatal day 1 in neonates treated with dexamethasone or hydrocortisone and controls during early or late pregnancy (IHC, StAR, hematoxylin counterstain, 40×). **A.** The control group shows strong staining for the StAR marker (square-headed arrow) in all zones: ZG, ZF, and ZR; **B.** The EDx group shows a low distribution of StAR, especially in the zona glomerulosa, with a high number of cortical cells with nonreactive cytoplasm (arrow); **C.** The EHd group shows a high number of cortical cells stained with the StAR marker, especially in ZF (square-headed arrow); **D.** The LDx group shows the lowest expression of the StAR marker and infiltration of inflammatory cells (arrow); **E.** The LHd group shows cells in ZF darkly stained with StAR (square-headed arrow) and lightly stained cells (circle-headed arrow).

Table 1. Comparison of the total positivity of the StAR marker in the suprarenal cortex between pairs of groups by ANOVA with Tukey’s test and independent-samples *t*-test.

	Control		Dexamethasone		Hydrocortisone	
	Early	Late	Early	Late	Early	Late
Day 1	0.7662 ± 0.0692	0.7344 ± 0.0701	0.4592 ± 0.0720 ***	0.2193 ± 0.0336 ***	0.5450 ± 0.0978 ***	0.4630 ± 0.0754 ***
Day 15	0.7285 ± 0.0653 #	0.7020 ± 0.0465 #	0.4902 ± 0.0703 ***	0.2455 ± 0.0676 ***	0.6527 ± 0.0757 ***	0.5829 ± 0.0739 ***

Comparison between treatment vs. control groups: * *p* < 0.05; ** *p* < 0.01; *** *p* < 0.001.

Comparison between day 1 vs. day 15 age groups: # *p* < 0.05; ## *p* < 0.01; ### *p* < 0.001.

Comparison between dexamethasone vs. hydrocortisone groups: + *p* < 0.05; ++ *p* < 0.01; +++ *p* < 0.001.

Comparison between early vs. late pregnancy treatment groups: • *p* < 0.05; •• *p* < 0.01; ••• *p* < 0.001.

Figure 5. Immunohistochemical reaction of StAR protein expression in the suprarenal cortex at postnatal day 15 in neonates treated with dexamethasone or hydrocortisone during early or late pregnancy (IHC, StAR, hematoxylin counterstain, 40 \times). **A.** The control group shows ZF stained with the StAR marker (square-headed arrow); **B.** The EDx group shows a patchy distribution of the StAR marker with weak expression (circle-headed arrow); **C.** The EHd group shows a wide distribution in ZF and ZR but a low distribution in ZG; **D.** The LDx group shows weak StAR expression (circle-headed arrow); **E.** The LHd group shows a wide distribution of StAR across cortical zones (square-headed arrow).

the early and late control groups (ECont and LCont) at the same age ($p > 0.05$).

All neonates exposed prenatally during early or late pregnancy to dexamethasone or hydrocortisone showed a highly significant reduction in StAR protein expression compared with the control groups ($p < 0.001$). This reduction was more pronounced in dexamethasone-treated groups, particularly following late gestational exposure (LDx, 0.2193 ± 0.0336), compared with hydrocortisone-treated groups (LHd, 0.4630 ± 0.0754 , $p < 0.001$).

In the hydrocortisone-treated groups (EHd and LHd), StAR protein expression showed a significant increase at postnatal day 15 (0.6527 ± 0.0757 and 0.5829 ± 0.0739 , respectively) compared with day 1 ($p < 0.001$). In contrast, dexamethasone-treated groups showed no significant difference between day 1 and day 15 ($p > 0.05$).

Furthermore, late gestational exposure (LDx and LHd) resulted in lower StAR protein expression than early gestational exposure (EDx and EHd). Overall, dexamethasone exerted a significantly stronger suppressive effect on StAR expression compared with hydrocortisone ($p < 0.001$).

Figure 6. Immunofluorescent detection of TUNEL-positive cells in the suprarenal cortex of neonates at postnatal day 1 treated with dexamethasone or hydrocortisone and controls during early or late pregnancy (TUNEL stain, 10 \times). **a.** The control group at day 1 shows few apoptotic cells (red dots); **b.** The EDx group shows more apoptotic cells in ZG and ZF than in ZR; **c.** The EHd group shows few apoptotic cells in all zones; **d.** The LDx group shows the highest number of apoptotic cells in all zones; **e.** The LHd group shows fewer apoptotic cells than the LDx group.

TUNEL assay in suprarenal cortex

The results of the TUNEL assay in the treatment groups, including comparison of apoptotic cell counts with the control groups and among all experimental groups, are summarized in Figs 6, 7 and Table 2.

The TUNEL assay for apoptosis was performed to determine DNA fragmentation. In the postnatal groups at

days 1 and 15, TUNEL-positive nuclei appeared as red dots in the suprarenal cortex.

Quantitative analysis revealed that the control groups showed low numbers of apoptotic cells at day 1 (ECont, 6.9667 ± 3.0112 ; LCont, 7.5667 ± 2.4450) and a significant reduction at day 15 (3.5000 ± 1.8146 and 4.0000 ± 2.1971 , respectively; $p < 0.001$). No significant difference

Figure 7. Immunofluorescent detection of TUNEL-positive cells in the suprarenal cortex of neonates at postnatal day 15 treated with dexamethasone or hydrocortisone during early or late pregnancy (TUNEL stain, 10 \times). **a.** The control group shows few TUNEL-positive cells across all cortical zones, with non-apoptotic cells; **b.** The EDx group shows a high distribution of apoptotic cells in all zones; **c.** The EHd group shows few apoptotic cells; **d.** The LDx group shows a high number of apoptotic cells in all zones; **e.** The LHd group shows low levels of apoptotic cells with a homogeneous distribution.

was observed between the early and late control groups at the same age ($p > 0.05$).

All treated groups (EDx, LDx, EHd, and LHd) at both postnatal ages demonstrated a highly significant increase in apoptotic cell count compared with the control groups ($p < 0.001$). The highest apoptotic activity was observed in dexamethasone-treated groups, particularly following late

gestational exposure (LDx, 97.5333 ± 16.5794 at day 1 and 91.8333 ± 14.3095 at day 15). Apoptotic cells were more frequently found in the zona glomerulosa and gradually decreased toward the zona fasciculata and zona reticularis.

In the hydrocortisone-treated groups, apoptotic cell count showed a significant reduction at postnatal day 15 (EHd, 46.7667 ± 10.8966 ; LHd, 57.0667 ± 10.0719)

Table 2. Comparison of the mean count of apoptotic cells in the suprarenal cortex between pairs of groups by ANOVA with Tukey's test and independent-samples *t*-test.

	Control		Dexamethasone		Hydrocortisone	
	Early	Late	Early	Late	Early	Late
Day 1	6.9667 ± 3.0112	7.5667 ± 2.4450	76.8333 ± 17.2288 ***	97.5333 ± 16.5794 ***	59.5333 ± 9.2017 ***	69.7000 ± 11.9023 ***
Day 15	3.5000 ± 1.8146 ***	4.0000 ± 2.1971 ***	69.1667 ± 16.2885 ***	91.8333 ± 14.3095 ***	46.7667 ± 10.8966 ***	57.0667 ± 10.0719 ***

Comparison between treatment vs. control groups: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$.

Comparison between day 1 vs. day 15 age groups: # $p < 0.05$; ## $p < 0.01$; ### $p < 0.001$.

Comparison between dexamethasone vs. hydrocortisone groups: + $p < 0.05$; ++ $p < 0.01$; +++ $p < 0.001$.

Comparison between early vs. late pregnancy treatment groups: • $p < 0.05$; •• $p < 0.01$; ••• $p < 0.001$.

compared with day 1 ($p < 0.001$). In contrast, dexamethasone-treated groups showed no significant difference between day 1 and day 15 ($p > 0.05$).

Furthermore, dexamethasone-treated groups (EDx and LDx) showed significantly higher apoptotic cell counts compared with hydrocortisone-treated groups (EHd and LHd) at both ages ($p < 0.001$).

Discussion

Maternal steroid treatment, especially with GCs, has been shown to significantly affect the histological structure of suprarenal glands in fetal and neonatal rats. Studies indicate that administration of GCs during gestation leads to notable morphological alterations in the suprarenal glands of neonates, primarily characterized by atrophy and reduced steroidogenic function (Pofi and Tomlinson 2020; Salman et al. 2025). The present study provides a comparative illustration of two clinically important steroids across specific gestational times, filling an important knowledge gap. The findings exclusively demonstrate that the suprarenal cortex responds with specific drug- and time-dependent remodeling processes, which progress significantly between postnatal day 1 and day 15. These perspectives reveal that the adrenal gland in the late gestational period is highly susceptible to prolonged structural reprogramming, an observation that extends beyond the static findings of previous literature.

The 11β -HSD2 enzyme converts endogenous corticosteroids into inactive metabolites in the placenta. Exogenous corticosteroids cross the placenta readily, leading to high levels of corticosteroids in the fetus (Vidaeff et al. 2023). This leads to significant suppression of the HPA axis, resulting in a profound reduction in hormonal secretion (Weiss et al. 2023). Prolonged exposure to GCs can lead to suppression of ACTH, which is crucial for stimulating adrenal function. Suprarenal cortex atrophy results from this suppression. Consequently, this atrophy can impair cortisol secretion, leading to a state of suprarenal insufficiency. Suprarenal suppression is most commonly the result of exogenous steroids, a condition recently termed glucocorticoid-induced suprarenal insufficiency (GIAI) (Nachawi et al. 2024).

An important observation of the present study is that the effects of antenatal GCs are both gestational stage-dependent and time-dependent, as demonstrated by the differences between early and late gestational exposure, as well as between postnatal day 1 and day 15.

The most prominent changes in suprarenal histology varied between the type of steroid administered, whether dexamethasone or hydrocortisone, and the timing of administration, whether during early or late pregnancy. This agrees with Prete and Bancos (2021), who reported that the dose, duration, frequency, timing of administration, pharmacokinetics, and interaction with other medications are factors that affect GIAI. Moreover, GCs with longer half-lives and strong potency have the greatest suppressive effect on the HPA axis (Improda et al. 2025).

Notably, the more pronounced alterations seen in late gestational groups suggest increased vulnerability of the suprarenal cortex during its maturation phase, when the gland becomes functionally more active and therefore more sensitive to hormonal disruption.

In this study, marked variations were seen in the histological structure of the adrenal cortex between control and treated groups, most prominently in dexamethasone-treated groups. Various features of apoptosis, the presence of giant cells, necrosis with resorptive necrotic zones, degeneration, the appearance of degenerative ghost cells, lymphocyte infiltration, and vascular dilatation with hemorrhage were observed. These histological changes have also been supported by Crowley et al. (2014), who noted the relationship between GC administration, whether endogenous or exogenous, and its binding to specific receptors in both the hypothalamus and pituitary, leading to negative feedback on ACTH release and suppression, resulting in impaired cortisol secretion.

Mechanistically, the pronounced disparity between dexamethasone and hydrocortisone effects, particularly during late gestation, can be attributed to dexamethasone's ability to bypass the placental enzymatic barrier. Unlike hydrocortisone, dexamethasone acts as a poor substrate for 11β -HSD2, ensuring nearly unrestricted fetal exposure. This massive ACTH deficit is the primary survival factor for adrenal cells. It is proposed that this ACTH deprivation directly explains the severe StAR protein suppression observed in the present results.

Degenerative changes in the adrenal zones of the suprarenal gland were seen, with loss of cellular arrangement in response to treatment, leading to difficulties in identifying the cortical zones according to their histological features, specifically in the inner part of the cortex, including the zona fasciculata and zona reticularis, most prominently in the late dexamethasone-treated group. This was reported in a previous study by Hristić et al. (1997), in which dexamethasone administered in late pregnancy in rats, start-

ing from day 16 until the end of pregnancy, demonstrated difficulties in recognizing the zona fasciculata (ZF) and zona reticularis (ZR). This zonal resorption and fusion ultimately led to volume reduction that extended to postnatal day 15.

The present results showed that lymphocytes were present until postnatal day 15 in the dexamethasone-treated group. Other studies reported a reduced number or absence of lymphocytes observed in the ZG of neonatal rats at day 14 in neonates treated with 1.5 mg/kg body weight. Another study mentioned that on postnatal day 14, multinucleated giant cells, lymphocytes, and resorption zones were absent in both control and experimental rats, but multinucleated giant cells were observed as necrotic cells between the medulla and ZR. Those rats were treated with 0.3 mg/kg/day starting from day 16 until the end of gestation. These variations are most probably related to variation in the dose and duration of treatment (Hristić et al. 1997). Moreover, even a single dose of dexamethasone given to pregnant rats during the critical period of HPA system development leads to prominent changes in both the structure and function of the suprarenal cortex in offspring, which continued for a long period after birth (Hristić et al. 1995).

Similarly, the present results on the effects of GCs encountered in the adult suprarenal gland, with dexamethasone treatment, showed degenerative changes involving shrinkage in the thickness of the three cortical zones due to cytoplasmic degeneration, pyknosis, and fibrosis with congestion of blood vessels. Moreover, treatment with hydrocortisone is rarely reported in the literature during the prenatal period, but research on the adult rat adrenal gland treated with hydrocortisone showed shrinkage in the thickness of its cortical zones and loss of normal organization, with cytoplasmic vacuolation (El-Refaiy 2019).

The StAR protein has a crucial role in the synthesis of steroid hormones in the suprarenal gland and other steroidogenic tissues. StAR facilitates cholesterol passage from the outer membrane to the mitochondria, which is the step that limits the rate of steroidogenesis. Pregnenolone is formed by the conversion of cholesterol inside the mitochondria by P450_{scc} (CYP11A1), the first enzymatic step in steroidogenesis. StAR enhances this process by increasing cholesterol availability. StAR expression is rapidly induced by ACTH via cAMP signaling in suprarenal cortical cells (Bremer and Miller 2014). The melanocortin 2 receptor (MC2R) is a G protein receptor that binds to ACTH, resulting in cAMP production and protein kinase A activation, which modifies the activity of transcription factors (Chourpiliadis and Aeddula 2020).

GCs bind to GR, which then enters the nucleus and modulates gene expression responsible for control of the HPA axis (Al-Rajhi et al. 2025; Ali et al. 2025). This includes suppressing CRH release from the hypothalamus and ACTH from the pituitary gland and inhibiting the activity of the G protein receptor, MC2R, cAMP production, and the steroid formation pathway within the adrenal gland (Nicolaidis et al. 2020). GC receptors are mainly

located in the zona fasciculata and, to a lesser extent, in the zona reticularis, and mediate the action of ACTH on adrenal cortical cells; this ultimately affects StAR expression (Angelousi et al. 2020).

The powerful effect of antenatal GC treatment on StAR protein suppression is more pronounced in dexamethasone-treated groups, especially in late-phase treatments.

This marked suppression of StAR protein expression, demonstrated in dexamethasone-treated groups, particularly during late gestation, is explained by the higher affinity of the GR, its longer half-life, and its resistance to placental inactivation by 11 β -HSD2, allowing greater fetal exposure compared with hydrocortisone. This leads to strong ACTH suppression and, consequently, reduces stimulation of StAR-dependent steroidogenesis.

Collectively, these findings indicate that dexamethasone causes more profound biological HPA axis disruption compared with hydrocortisone, leading to a greater reduction in ACTH-dependent steroidogenesis and enhanced activation of apoptotic pathways within the suprarenal cortex.

Moreover, Kater et al. (2022) explained that prenatal stress can lead to DNA methylation or histone modifications at the StAR promoter region, causing persistent suppression even after birth. This may contribute to impaired steroidogenesis in adulthood, such as suprarenal insufficiency and altered gonadal function.

A similar effect was found in hydrocortisone treatment during gestation on the expression of StAR protein in the adrenal cortex. This contributed to downregulation of the corticotropic receptors affected by suppression of the HPA axis. This is supported by a study on gene expression of receptors and enzymes involved in intracellular cholesterol availability and enzymes involved in corticosterone synthesis, including steroidogenic acute regulatory protein, CYP11A1, and CYP11B1, which were lower in the hydrocortisone-treated group compared with the placebo-treated group (Téblick et al. 2022).

The present results showed that the reduction in StAR immunohistochemical expression at postnatal day 15 is mainly due to the extended effect of prenatal treatment with GCs on suppression of StAR protein expression. This was confirmed by a study by He et al. (2023), which showed that prenatal dexamethasone exposure (PDE) can further inhibit adrenal steroidogenesis, and this effect can be transmitted by oocytes to subsequent generations of rats due to its genetic stability, as second-generation oocytes indirectly exposed to dexamethasone could transmit this effect to the third generation.

This marked suppression of StAR expression acts as a biochemical blockade of cholesterol transport, which is hypothesized to serve as a primary pro-apoptotic trigger. The resulting metabolic failure, combined with the lack of ACTH-mediated survival signals, likely activates mitochondrial apoptotic pathways (Bax/Bak/Bid), culminating in extensive DNA fragmentation, as evidenced by the TUNEL results. This explains why dexamethasone exposure induces more severe apoptotic remodeling than hydrocortisone; it effectively disables the ACTH–StAR

signaling axis, on which the maturing adrenal gland becomes increasingly dependent during late pregnancy.

Apoptosis involves DNA fragmentation, which triggers cell death, and is the measure of the cell's ultimate demise. The terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase dUTP nick-end labeling (TUNEL) assay is a method for assessing apoptosis by DNA fragmentation, in which DNA strand breaks are enzymatically labeled with modified nucleotides at their free 3'-OH termini (Mohan et al. 2014).

The higher apoptotic activity observed in dexamethasone-treated groups, particularly in late gestation, may be attributed to enhanced mitochondrial apoptotic pathway activation and increased vulnerability of the developing suprarenal cortex during this critical maturation period.

The present results showed the presence of multinucleated giant cells in the vicinity of resorption zones, with numerous lymphocyte infiltrations and fibrosis, in the gland cortex of dexamethasone-treated groups, indicating apoptotic (nuclear pyknosis) and necrotic changes seen in resorption zones in both early and late treated groups at days 1 and 15. This reflects that prolonged dexamethasone administration to pregnant rats affects the fetal hypothalamo-hypophyseal system and inhibits the proliferation of suprarenal cortical cells (Hristić et al. 1997).

Furthermore, previous studies have demonstrated structural changes consistent with the present findings, including zonal degeneration, apoptotic cells, and necrotic tissue, with apparent ultrastructural changes including nuclear pyknosis, chromatin aggregation, and reduction in cell volume reflecting apoptotic changes. Increased TUNEL-positive cells were also observed in the ZR and ZF in dexamethasone-treated animals compared with controls, with higher expression of caspase-3, indicating activation of apoptotic pathways (Almeida et al. 2006; Liu et al. 2018). The present results showed that hydrocortisone increased apoptosis, but to a lesser extent than dexamethasone. Similar findings have been reported in experimental models, where hydrocortisone treatment was associated with increased apoptotic activity and impaired adrenal function compared with controls (De Bruyn et al. 2023).

Study limitations

The present study has certain limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the sample size is relatively limited,

which affects the generalizability of the findings. Second, the study did not include long-term postnatal follow-up and focused on a specific developmental time. Third, the present study was specifically designed to assess structural and molecular alterations in the suprarenal cortex, while maternal serum GCs were not measured during pregnancy or in neonatal rats. Fourth, clinical and systemic postnatal outcomes were not the primary focus of the present study, which was specifically designed to assess histological and molecular changes in the neonatal adrenal cortex. Fifth, this study used an animal model (*Rattus norvegicus*), and therefore, the findings may not be directly extrapolated to human physiology. Although animal models provide valuable insights into developmental and mechanistic processes, species-specific differences should be considered when interpreting results in a clinical context.

Conclusion

Significant structural and molecular changes in the neonatal adrenal cortex were observed following prenatal GC exposure in a time- and drug-dependent manner. Dexamethasone showed more profound effects than hydrocortisone, particularly when administered during late gestation, where its effect lasted until postnatal day 15. These alterations in the suprarenal cortex included adrenal atrophy, increased apoptosis, and reduced StAR protein expression, possibly related to direct GR activation and impaired ACTH regulation.

Changes in the suprarenal cortex favor impaired tissue-level steroidogenic capacity; however, further studies, including hormonal assessment, are required to confirm the functional impact.

Future studies are recommended to investigate long-term postnatal outcomes and include a larger sample size to further validate these findings.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Data availability

The datasets generated and analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.